

Open Science NL

Open Research Software Advisory Panel

Meeting Notes

20 February 2026, 15:00-17:00

Location: MS Teams

Attendees

- Ana Martinovici (AM)
- Daniel S. Katz (DSK)
- Daniela Gawehns (DG)
- John Swinbank (JS)
- Laurents Sesink (LS)
- Martine de Vos (MdV)
- Mateusz Kuzak (MK)
- Morane Gruenpeter (MG)
- Santosh Ilamparuthi (SI)
- Vincent Traag (VT) (from 4pm)
- Mark van Assem (MvA) - Acting Co-Chair
- Marta Teperek (MT) - Acting Chair

Apologies

- Thomas Pronk
- Maria Cruz, Chair

Absent

- Karthik Ram

Notes

Welcome and agenda

MT welcomed everyone. The agenda was approved. MT informed panel members that minutes of the last meeting had been published on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18151097>

Actions of the previous meeting

MT informed the panel that the meeting with the NWO Advisory Panel Computer Science to discuss support for open source software projects was scheduled for 15 April. AM and VT from the panel will attend. AM reiterated that any input from panel members should be directed to her and VT.

Update on the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025

MT updated panel members on the progress of the implementation of the OSNL Work Programme 2024-2025:

- Open Science Infrastructure and Replication Studies Programme calls were awarded
- Funding to the NLeSC for the Research Software Sustainability Programme was awarded
- The decision on the Research on Open Science call for proposals will be made on 20 March

MT and MvA also provided additional explanation to the panel about the budget increase for the Open Science Infrastructure call, and summarised some discussions around the budget increase.

Panel members were pleased to hear that the call budget was increased and more projects were awarded as a result.

DG mentioned that the Dutch Reproducibility Network will be organising an event for the grantees of the Replication Studies Programme.

Advisory panel – going forward

The Open Science NL Steering Board advised to merge the Open Research Software and FAIR Data panels into a single advisory panel.

To ensure that there was sufficient time and space to discuss matters relevant only to research software and only to research data, the Board advised to:

- Allocate sufficient time in the agenda for discussions pertaining to open research software/research data
- Consider adding a few additional members (above 12) if additional expertise turns out to be necessary
- Consider planning separate meetings dedicated to software/data if this is necessary/desirable

The board suggested that the name of the merged panel needs to be inclusive of the broadened scope of the merged panel.

Planning of dedicated agenda items and dedicated meetings

MT explained that any panel member can suggest new agenda items or dedicated meetings. For adding agenda items, suggestions need to be made in writing at least 2 weeks before the meeting date via an email to the chair of the meeting.

Expertise of panel members

Panel members were asked to provide advice on whether the merged panel will continue to have sufficient content expertise pertaining to open research software. *Appendix 1: Profiles panel members* details the desired profiles of panel members as per the current OSNL Community Engagement Strategy. Panel members were asked if the key expertise as detailed in *Appendix 1: Profiles panel members* was up to date, or if any key areas of expertise were missing.

The following points were raised:

- The Community Engagement Strategy and panel profiles needed updating; some topics (e.g. open hardware) were in the wrong panels.
- Several bullet points overlapped (e.g. publication/citation includes licensing) – the list was perhaps too detailed and could be described at a higher level.
- It felt essential that members of the panel were aware of the institutional context. For example, representation from Universities of Applied Sciences was currently missing.
- New focus areas may need inclusion, such as sustainable infrastructure business models.
- Many topics (career paths, digital sovereignty, AI) cut across panels.
- OSPOs were discussed as potentially relevant for software tracking and support; however, some other panel members noted that the focus of the panel was on research software.
 - It was agreed that a dedicated meeting with SURF will be planned for those interested in the situation around the OSPOs.
- A concern was raised that with MK and DG stepping down from the panel, expertise on skills and training pertaining to research software might be missing.
- Decisions about any missing skills will be made at the first joint advisory panel meeting once the new composition, skills and experiences are known. A merged skills list will be shared before that meeting for input.

Tenure of remaining panel members

MT asked if any of the panel members whose term expires in 2027 (panel members appointed for 3 years) would be prepared to stay for an additional year (thus, 4 years in total). This would help ensure continuity of the work of the panel and avoid the event that all panel members step down at the same time in 2027. MG explained that she would step down after the initial term of 3 years. Other panel members would be prepared to extend their initial term duration for an additional year. Panel members suggested that MT as the chairperson suggests which panel members would be invited to stay for an additional year.

Name of the panel

MT explained that the name of the new merged panel should be inclusive of data, software and hardware perspectives. Several possible names were suggested including:

- Open Data, Software, and Hardware
- Open (Research) Data, Software and Hardware.
- Digital technologies in research (which would combine data, software and infrastructure perspectives)
- Open Research Artifacts or Open Research Materials
- Verifiable Science (is also a statement), but might be not inclusive of some disciplines in the humanities.
- Research Outputs. Makes a bigger statement. Differentiates us from Science in general.

Pros and cons of various names were discussed and it was concluded that the discussion will be finalised during the first meeting of the merged panel.

Thank you to the outgoing panel members

MT cordially thanked all panel members whose term was ending: Daniela Gawehns, Laurents Sesink, John Swinbank, Karthik Ram, Vincent Traag and Mateusz Kuzak. MT mentioned that their contribution to the work of OSNL was invaluable and their expertise was greatly appreciated.

Any other business

The group discussed how to organise the first meeting of the merged panel. Online meetings were generally preferred because they were more inclusive for all members, easier to attend, and avoided travel costs – especially since there is no budget available for travel. Physical or hybrid meetings were acknowledged as

potentially valuable, but not feasible for the first meeting. A future hybrid meeting (perhaps one a year) could be considered, ideally co-located with relevant European events that several members already attend. Possible events mentioned include conferences in Munich (Future of Open Research in Munich: <https://opensciencestudies.eu/for-2026-conference/>), Sheffield (International Research Software Conference), London (RDA Plenary), and an event at DANS in June in the Netherlands.

Meeting close

MT closed the meeting at 16.20.